

“Innovative and sustainable materials solutions for the substitution of critical raw materials (CRM) in the electric power systems, in particular CRM in materials used in photovoltaic cells”

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D7.4. Gender Action Plan

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1. Preliminary considerations and definitions

The following deliverable serves as a preliminary, common baseline for our understanding of the fields of action and gender equality within STARCELL.

Sex & Gender

Distinguishing between sex and gender is crucial, as it allows for a more nuanced understanding of gendered power relations and gender inequalities. First, sex refers to the biological differences between women and men based on primary and secondary sexual characteristics (*Humbert, Ivaškaitė-Tamošiūnė, Oetke & Paats, 2015, p. 8*). It is important to note however, that while biological sex is often understood as the biological condition of being either ‘male’ or ‘female’ – implying a binary – this is not necessarily the case (e.g. intersex individuals). On the other hand, gender refers to the socially constructed, historically, culturally, and spatially specific meaning attached to the perceived binary distinction between the sexes; in other words ‘femininity’ and ‘masculinity’ (*Humbert et al., 2015*). Contrary to popular perception, gender does not describe binary categories, but has to be seen as fluid. Understanding gender as “something fluid, something continuously changing, not an inherent characteristic of a person” (*Danielsson, 2012, p. 27*) helps question the power structures underlying our societies.

Gender Equality

Gender equality means different things to different people and can thus be interpreted in many different ways. Commonly, a distinction is made between three different approaches. Gender Equality can refer to making women equal to men (**sameness-approach**), it can focus on highlighting women as a separate group with inherent qualities that need to be supported (**difference approach**) or it can refer to changing the way gender influences our society by transforming gender relations and cultures, thus inherently changing the status quo (**transformative-approach**) (*Rees, 2006; Verloo & Lombardo, 2007; Munday, 2009*).

In order to build effective gender equality plans, we need to establish what exactly is searched to achieve. In other words: how do we imagine gender equality to look like within STARCELL? The project aims at inspiring structural institutional and cultural change to make gender equality a reality in the field of photovoltaics. As such, STARCELL aims at addressing the European Research Areas goals of mainstreaming gender in research, resolving implicit biases and removing barriers to women’s access to scientific careers. The first approach, focusing on making women equal to men, does not satisfy these aims, as the dimension of biases and imbalanced power relations is not considered. The second does not provide a good fit either. While measures supporting women as a ‘group’ certainly are an important aspect of counteracting present and past structural inequalities, emphasizing women’s difference comes with the risk of further stereotypes. Furthermore, as objectivity is key in the natural sciences such as physics and materials science, emphasizing women’s difference as a claim to equality, will likely be rejected by both female and male scientists, as they feel that differences in abilities do not exist and as a consequence, differences in (work) treatment should not exist. It follows that a transformative approach and understanding of gender equality, targeting culture and practices as a way to achieve the needed transformation within the field, is the most valuable approach. Moreover, it allows us to question the underlying dynamics hindering women in their career progressions, enabling a more holistic approach to gender equality.

2. STARCELL: Fields of Action

The promotion of gender equality within the Consortium is a strong commitment of the teams involved in the project, in line with the strategy of H2020. In particular, the following long-term objectives are pursued:

- Fostering gender balance in innovation and research teams, in order to close the gaps in the participation of women;
- Searching for gender balance in decision-making processes;
- Integrating the gender dimension in research and innovation (R&I) activities.

These objectives underpin the European Commission determination to implement gender equality in Horizon 2020 actions at each stage of the research and innovation cycle.

Gender balance in research teams at all levels

The Consortium will promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of STARCELL activities at different stages of the innovation cycle, in line with the Article 33 of the Grant Agreement on “Gender Equality”. To overcome the problem of the lack of women in science and reinforce gender balance, STARCELL partners will follow the strategy to prioritize women with equivalent CVs. To that end, gender-sensitive formulation of advertisements for open positions should be published and a complete transparency of the selection procedures guaranteed. On the other hand, the exemplary measures and instruments listed in the table below should be applied by each beneficiary in line with their internal and National regulations:

3. Bibliography and acknowledgements

Humbert, A.L., Ivaškaitė-Tamošiūnė, V., Oetke, N., & Paats, M. (2015). Gender Equality Index 2015 – Measuring gender equality in the European Union 2005-2012: Report. Vilnius, Lithuania: European Institute for Gender Equality. Retrieved from <http://www.eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/mh0215616enn.pdf>

Danielsson, A. T. (2012). Exploring woman university physics students ‘doing gender’ and ‘doing physics’. *Gender and Education*, 24(1), pp. 25-39. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09540253.2011.565040>

Rees, T. (2006). Reflections on the uneven development of gender mainstreaming in Europe. *International Feminist Journal of Politics*, 7(4), pp. 555-574. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14616740500284532>

Verloo, M., & Lombardo, E. (2007). Contested gender equality in Europe: Introducing a critical frame analysis approach. In Verloo Mieke, *Multiple meanings of gender equality – A critical frame analysis of gender policies in Europe* (21-49). Budapest: CEU Press.

Munday, J. (2009). Gendered citizenship. *Sociological Compass*, 3(2), 249-266. doi:10.1111/j.17519020.2008.00187.x

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Structural and Integration Policies				
Policies		Monitoring		Gender Composition
1.	Compliance with National Regulations	1.	Evaluation of HR policies	1. Ensuring that all bodies are gender-sensitive and aware
2.	Internal Gender Equality Plans	2.	Evaluation of organizational culture	
3.	Presence of labour unions & HR representatives	3.	Employee surveys & gender statistics	
Flexibility, Time and Work Life				
Work-Life Balance (WLB)		Care & Family Life		
1.	Reasonable working ours, limited overtime	1.	Parental leaves: "father quota"	
2.	Move key meetings to core hours (family responsibilities)	2.	Parent-friendly workplaces	
3.	Equal treatment of part-time positions	3.	Non-discrimination of parents	
4.	Flexible schedules			
5.	Avoidance of "Old-boys clubs"			
Presence and Visibility				
1.	Gender-sensitive language			
2.	Men and women as contributors of collaborative works/papers			
3.	Equal treatment of part-time work			
4.	Career and life planning			